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**Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning
FEMaLe**

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Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning: FEMaLe

1. INTRODUCTION

Responsible Research and Innovation and Open Science

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is a term used by policy makers and academics to refer to research and innovation that are ethically acceptable and socially desirable (Gurzawska et al., 2017). It is a process that seeks to promote creativity and opportunities for science and innovation that are beneficial and undertaken in the public interest (UKRI, 2023).

In 2001, the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation of the European Commission (EC) decided to bridge the gap between the scientific community and the society by launching the Science and Society Action plan (European Commission, 2012). This subsequently led to several research and technological development programmes, including ELSA (ethical, legal, and social aspects) and Science in Society (SiS), whose main objective was to promote public engagement through dialogue between science and civil society (Burget et al., 2017; Owen et al., 2012).

In 2010, the focus shifted to develop a concept that balances the need for innovation with societal needs: A Framework for Responsible Research and Innovation. The term made a breakthrough in many high-level policy, strategy, and programming documents, such as the Europe 2020 Strategy and the Horizon 2020 framework (European Commission. Directorate General for Research., 2013; Owen et al., 2012).

Research and innovation have nowadays become one of the main pillars of the EU strategy as it help create growth and prosperity while finding solutions to some of society's biggest challenges, such as climate change, demographic change, well-being, energy security, food security and safe societies (Gurzawska et al., 2017). The EU recognises these challenges and aspires to RRI as a potential solution to them. In doing so, using RRI approaches can help improve the value of publicly funded research for the benefit of society (Gurzawska et al., 2017).

On the other hand, Open Science is a relatively new paradigm that promotes the principles of transparency, accessibility, and collaboration in scientific research (Grand et al., 2012). Open Science is a movement that aims to make scientific research, including sharing of data, methods, and results, accessible to all levels of society, regardless of their affiliation, in order to promote scientific progress and innovation (UNESCO, 2023).

Moreover, it allows researchers to build upon the work of others and disseminate their findings more widely, ultimately leading to more significant progress and innovation in the research field (Committee on Toward an Open Science Enterprise et al., 2018). Also, Open Science can foster collaboration among researchers across different fields and disciplines, leading to more innovative and interdisciplinary research.

Open Science and RRI can together have a transformative impact on scientific research and innovation, and both terms seem to be extremely useful for the ability to respond to societal challenges. Open Science can foster collaboration, knowledge-sharing, and accelerate scientific progress (UNESCO, 2023), while RRI ensures that the research is conducted in an ethical and socially responsible manner (Gurzawska et al., 2017).

Furthermore, by involving stakeholders in the research process, Open Science and RRI can enhance public trust in science and research, by making research more accessible and understandable to the public (Lakomý et al., 2019; Shelley-Egan et al., 2020). This trust is fundamental, particularly due to the many complex and controversial scientific issues that society faces today, which makes Open Science and RRI essential.

Open science and RRI are fundamental for our society

To address major societal challenges, all actors should be fully engaged in the co-construction of innovative solutions, products, and services. To achieve this, the EC has developed a framework to respond to societal challenges, consisting of six key elements: public engagement, gender equality, science education, ethics, open access and governance (European Commission, 2012).

Public engagement creates a healthy framework in which societal challenges are tackled through mutual learning and shared practice. This is recognised as essential for developing common solutions to societal problems and creates opportunities to anticipate the potential public value of future innovation. It involves the engagement of all societal actors, including researchers, policy makers, industry, and civil society (European Commission, 2012).

Furthermore, the involvement of civil society implies the inclusion of all actors, regardless of sex, and gender, to unlock the full potential in research. Therefore, gender equality in research is necessary, addressing, for example, the underrepresentation of women, as described in the FEMaLe *white paper on gender-based and inclusive health and care systems* (D2.3).

To facilitate the involvement of citizen in research, the European Citizen Science Association has created ten principles for sharing good practice and building capacity in citizen science (Gold, 2022). The concept of citizen science is designed to be flexible and can be adapted and applied in diverse situations, disciplines, and as a part of education. Inviting citizens into research not only helps equip future scientists and other societal actors, but also fosters creative thinking and develops children's interest in science.

Another way to help improve the future of research and accelerate innovation is by making research accessible to all. Open access means providing free online access to research results and data from publicly funded research. This not only creates value for other researchers but also provides economic value to society.

Additionally, the FAIR data principles have been developed as a guideline to improve the reusability of data holdings. The FAIR data principles ensure that data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, and have become an integrated element of the Horizon programme (European Commission, 2016). Making data FAIR involves the creation of a data management plan (DMP), which is a key element of good data management and describes how data will be collected, processed, and generated.

However, research and innovation must also respect fundamental rights and adhere to high ethical and legal standards. Ethics should not be seen as a constraint to research and innovation but rather to ensure high-quality results, as described in the FEMaLe *white paper on ethical health and care systems* (D2.2) Finally, the government has a responsibility to prevent unethical developments and uphold the standards.

This highlights the importance of open science and RRI in our society as it helps promote transparency, accessibility, and social responsibility in scientific research, leading to greater progress and more innovative solutions. In this report, we aim to bring together experiences to better understand open science and RRI from an international perspective, which can help develop an updated set of recommendations to improve how we collect and work with data.

2. AIM

The aim of this paper is to gain a deeper understanding of how to work with Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation in a European project and provide an overview of how this impacts the project's results. Based on these findings, the paper aims to provide recommendations for future actions.

3. DEFINITIONS

3.1 Responsible Research and Innovation

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is an approach that promotes public involvement throughout the research and innovation process. The approach aims to ensure that scientific and technological advances are aligned with societal needs, values, and expectations (TetRRIs, 2021).

RRI emphasises the importance of anticipating and reflecting on the potential impacts, ethical implications, and broader consequences of research and innovation activities (Jakobsen et al., 2019).

3.2 Open Science

Open science refers to a collaborative and transparent approach to scientific research that aims to make knowledge, research, data, and their dissemination available to any member of society, from professionals to citizens (Orion Open Science, 2017).

This includes making research processes and outcomes findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable by anyone who is interested (European Commission, 2023).

Open science aims to foster innovation, accelerate scientific progress, and address societal challenges by removing barriers to accessing and using scientific knowledge.

4. CHALLENGES

The world is constantly changing, which has led to many positive developments in research activities and innovative solutions. To ensure solutions are conducted in an ethical and socially responsible manner, Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) can serve as an important foundation. However, there are still challenges when it comes to implementing these principles in practice.

One of the first challenges is the **lack of data sharing**, which poses several challenges to open science and responsible research and innovation. Open science and responsible research require that scientific findings and methodologies are transparent and reproducible. Without access to the underlying data, it becomes difficult, even impossible, for other researchers to replicate and verify the results (Miyakawa, 2020). This hinders the progress of science, as it relies on the ability to build upon existing knowledge.

A second challenge is the **lack of funding**, which can be a significant problem when it comes to making data openly available. The limited availability of resources affects the ability to conduct high-quality and comprehensive research. Therefore, adequate funding is essential to support research activities, including data collection, equipment, materials, and personnel (Neema & Chandrashekar, 2021). Open science aims to make scientific knowledge and research outcomes accessible to a wide range of stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, and the public (Grand et al., 2012). However, without sufficient funding, researchers may face difficulties in making their research outputs freely available, such as publishing in open-access journals or covering publication fees. This can hinder the accessibility and affordability of research outputs, limiting their impact and potential benefits. Insufficient funding can also restrict the ability of researchers to establish and sustain collaborations, especially across disciplines and institutions.

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The third, and potentially largest, challenge is the **lack of involvement** in inviting citizen into the research process. Especially in the field of endometriosis, open science and responsible research require diverse perspectives and expertise to address this complex societal challenge (Endomarch, 2023).

Insufficient involvement means that valuable insights, experiences, and knowledge from different stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, industry professionals, and the public, may be overlooked. This limitation hampers the ability to develop comprehensive and effective solutions.

Additionally, the lack of involvement can lead to oversight of ethical concerns, such as potential risks, privacy issues, or the impact on marginalized communities (Resnik & Elliott, 2016).

Involving a broader range of stakeholders ensures that ethical considerations are adequately addressed and integrated into the research process.

Furthermore, by involving the public in scientific decision-making processes fosters transparency, trust, and public acceptance of research outcomes. When the public is engaged, their concerns, values, and perspectives can be incorporated into research activities (Canfield et al., 2020).

This involvement enhances the legitimacy of scientific concerns and facilitates the acceptance and adoption of research findings in society, while also contributing to the development of more sustainable solutions that have a greater benefit for society.

The fourth challenge is the **lack of FemTech**, referring to technology and innovation specifically targeting women's health and well-being, which can perpetuate gender bias and contribute to health inequities (Behimino, 2021; Mastantuono, 2022). Women's health needs and experiences are often overlooked or underrepresented in medical research and innovation.

FemTech plays a crucial role in addressing these gaps by focusing on female-specific health issues, such as reproductive health, menstrual health, pregnancy, menopause, and sexual health (Rosencrance, 2023). Without dedicated attention to women's health, there is a risk of neglecting important health concerns and perpetuating gender disparities in healthcare.

Furthermore, FemTech represents a rapidly growing market with significant economic potential (FemTech Analytics, 2023). The absence of FemTech limits opportunities for innovation, entrepreneurship, and economic growth in this sector. Investing in FemTech can stimulate job creation, drive innovation, and improve health outcomes for women, benefiting both the economy and society at large.

To promote more accessible and open research, there is a need to change how we collect, work with, and process data. There are several **opportunities** to influence multiple parts of society. By developing strategies to address the above challenges, we can better realise the **potentials** of our work within research, organisations, and political ambitions, and thus achieve an impact faster and more effectively.

5. CASES

The following section will present five examples of how the FEMaLe project is working with *Open Science* and *RRI*. The purpose of these examples is to showcase how to involve citizens in research, innovation, and data sharing, which is useful for both the research process itself and for the people involved. The examples also illustrate areas for improvement and provide further recommendations.

Case 1: Citizen Science workshop for Academy for Talented Youth Students

In close collaboration with the state-of-the-art science communication and research project '[Giving Young People a Voice](#)' under the auspices of the Department of Public Health at Aarhus University, FEMaLe project organised three workshops in March 2023, with a total of 52 Danish high school students participating. The workshops were part of a dedicated seminar on *Citizen Science*, which invited young people to participate as co-creators in new research projects.

The purpose of the workshop was to engage high school students as co-researchers in developing a citizen health science project about young people and menstrual health, with emphasis on involving young people in formulating and prioritising research questions, participating in data collection and analysis, as well as communicating new insights and findings to the public and policy-makers.

Citizen science refers to the involvement of the public, often non-professional scientists, in scientific research projects (Smallman, 2018). In citizen science, volunteers, known as *citizen scientists*, work alongside professional scientists, researchers, or organizations to contribute their time, effort, and expertise to gather data or perform specific tasks that help advance scientific knowledge. Some of the benefits using this method is the public engagement, fostering a sense of ownership, empowerment, and interest in science for those participating (Von Gönner et al., 2023).

Citizen science projects can further create a sense of community and collaboration among participants, allowing them to connect with like-minded individuals and work towards a common goal (Smallman, 2018). Citizen science appeared to be a very valuable approach to democratise scientific research, engage the public in scientific inquiry, and generate a wealth of data that can contribute to scientific knowledge and societal well-being.

The intention of the project was to get engage young people in a taboo topic and to increase their awareness of and interest in menstrual health. Our ideology is based on the idea that to understand the students' experience of life and to integrate such valuable perspectives in a project, the students themselves must be involved in developing it.

Ultimately, the three workshops resulted in several useful discussions, as described in the FEMaLe *white paper on gender-based and inclusive health and care systems* (D2.3). Further, we recruited several young people ready to take part in the upcoming project, as they found the workshop fun, relevant and educational, especially the citizen health science approach.

Case 2: Reaching consensus on the most relevant symptoms for endometriosis

Work packages 3 in the FEMaLe project prepared a sub-study aiming at reaching consensus on the most relevant symptoms for endometriosis. The objective was to develop a set of questions on symptoms and related consequences that could be used to identify women with suspected and confirmed endometriosis, with the help of a panel of endometriosis experts.

To accomplish this, the group decided to use the Delphi method, which is a structured technique that relies on input from a panel of experts. These experts respond to the same set of questions in two or more rounds.

After each round, an anonymized summary of the experts' answers from the previous round is provided. Experts are therefore encouraged to revise their earlier responses based on the inputs of the other experts, with the aim of reaching a consensus through a collaborative approach.

The Delphi study was planned to include two rounds and included doctors, patients, and researchers with expert knowledge in endometriosis. Participants from Denmark, Hungary, the UK, France, and Turkey were included in the study.

The participants were asked to consider the relevance of 107 symptoms from a baseline questionnaire, using the following options: “not relevant”, “slightly relevant”, “relevant”, “very relevant”, “necessary” or “unsure/outside my area of expertise”.

A total of 76 experts participated in the first round (43 patients and 33 doctors/researchers) and 65 experts participated in the second round (38 patients and 27 doctors/researchers) of the consensus study. After the first round of the consensus study, four symptoms were found relevant. Following the second round, another two symptoms/related consequences were identified.

The co-creation process with the three groups of experts has contributed to a broader understanding of the symptoms associated with endometriosis. The diverse perspectives provided interesting insights into the disease for the researchers and made the patients and practitioners who participated in the study more aware of each other's perspectives and experiences.

The study is considered an innovative research process that involves public engagement and where the results better support societal needs.

Case 3: Lucy App: Advanced period tracker

The Lucy App is our mobile health tracking application, which can be used to monitor self-reported endometriosis, mental health, physical activity, and environmental factors. It aims to identify behavioural patterns underlying clinical manifestations in people with endometriosis, specifically related to stress, infertility issues, nutritional factors, and other lifestyle factors.

The Lucy App includes a menstruation and fertility calendar to help women keep track of their menstrual cycle and fertility, sending alerts if the users' need to consult a gynaecologist based on their symptoms.

The app was created in collaboration with the Hungarian patient's organisation 'Together it's easier' For Women's Health Foundation, the technology company YourCode Lab. It has been supervised by specialist Dr. Attila Bokor, PhD, and obstetrician gynaecologist.

Together, they have developed an algorithm that monitors users' reported symptoms related to determine if they should visit their gynaecologist. The algorithm is designed to identify symptoms related to endometriosis, PCOS, Myoma, Ovarian cyst, Pelvic inflammation, Diabetes and IRISH.

Furthermore, this group has co-developed the Lucy Questionnaire, which allows us to collect data from users and develop patient profiles and structured clinical data. This data collection is not only relevant to Lucy App users but will also have a significant impact on the classification of new patterns of endometriosis.

The application also collects information from the user's post and created a summary, which the patient can show to a doctor, providing a more accurate picture of the user's medical condition and enabling better treatment. The diary feature in the Lucy app can:

- Help with family planning by letting the user know about their fertility days,
- Notify the user before the expected menstruation,
- Notify the user if they can expect PMS symptoms,
- Remind the user to take their contraceptive – or other medication – in time,
- For pregnant users, Lucy helps with pregnancy tracking, and
- Help with weight change tracking.

During the app’s development, we focused on making it accessible to as many users as possible. Therefore, the app is available in multiple languages (Hungarian, Danish, Swedish and English) and is free to download on Android and iOS.

The app has already made a significant impact for the patients, with an average of 6-7,000 active users per month. Users register 15,000 symptoms and 8,000 events monthly, and they have read available articles 500 times, mainly about Endometriosis and Cervical Mucus.

The reviews and feedbacks are overwhelmingly positive, with ratings ranging from 4.6 to 4.7 out of 5. For more information about the period tracker, please visit: <https://hellolucy.app/en> (in English).

Case 4: Data Management Plan

The project has created an initial data management plan (DMP), which has been subsequently updated.

The aim of the DMP is to outline the project's approach to analysing, storing, and ensuring the reusability of all collected data.

The project strives to make the data as open as possible, so that others can benefit from it, while also ensuring that it remains appropriately protected to comply with regulatory guidelines. This commitment aligns with the principles of Open Science and Responsible Research & Innovation.

The FEMaLe project will generate a wide range of data across its ten work packages. The overall purpose of the data collection is to answer the objective of the FEMaLe project, as described in the proposal.

In developing the DMPs, the FEMaLe project complies to the FAIR data management concept, emphasising that project data should be: **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**e-usable.

To assist the creation of the initial and updated data management plans, we made use of the online tool: <https://dmponline.deic.dk/>. A dedicated data management representative from each of the ten work packages was assigned to provide an overview of the collected data within their respective work package, filling in the online survey.

The DMPonline questionnaire included 40 items related to the data collection, according to the FAIR principles. Initially, the data management responsible was asked to address issues related to the purpose, objective, types and formats, size, and utility of the collected data. Then, they were required to assess the extent to which the research data aligned with the FAIR data principles.

Through this comprehensive description, we aim to encourage all project partners to reflect on their data collection, analysis, and distribution processes, enabling as many people as possible to benefit from it.

Throughout the FEMaLe project, we will continue to collect data and engage FEMaLers in ongoing discussions about how to effectively align FEMaLe data with FAIR principles.

This commitment will support future projects and maximize the impact of the FEMaLe project.

Case 5: Joint FEMaLe and TRANSFORM project collaboration

During the ECSA (European Citizen Science Association) Conference from 5-8 October 2022 in Berlin in Germany, FEMaLe Liv Juul Nielsen presented a joint poster about *'Endometriosis and citizen health science: a new future for responsible research and innovation priority setting?'*, together with Diana Reinoso from Science for Change, part of the TRANSFORM H2020 project.

FEMaLe was standing on the shoulders of Andrew Horne, Philippa Saunders, Ibtisam Abokhrais and Lyndsey Hogg – on behalf of the whole Endometriosis Priority Setting Partnership Steering Group – who in 2017

published an article in *The Lancet* about endometriosis research priorities in the UK and Ireland:

CORRESPONDENCE | VOLUME 389, ISSUE 10085, P2191-2192, JUNE 03, 2017

Top ten endometriosis research priorities in the UK and Ireland

Andrew W Horne • Philippa T K Saunders • Ibtisam M Abokhrais • Lyndsey Hogg
on behalf of the Endometriosis Priority Setting Partnership Steering Group (appendix)

Published: May 18, 2017 • DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(17\)31344-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(17)31344-2)

Following the successful ECSA 2022 poster session, we continued the fruitful joint FEMaLe and TRANSFORM cross-H2020-project collaboration and conducted a webinar on 13 October 2022, highlighting the 'First-person experiences of endometriosis: Participatory research, needs and recommendations of people with endometriosis'. The TRANSFORM's Catalan cluster led a citizen science pilot project on endometriosis aiming at involving patients in co-creating recommendations for the improvement of healthcare services.

In this webinar, which was led by the Ulrik Bak Kirk, FEMaLe Coordinator, Diana Reinoso and Nora Salas Seoane from Science of Change presented the unique methodology, co-creation and participatory activities involving patients, as well as the challenges encountered and how they overcame them.

The results were presented along with specific recommendations for improving healthcare services for people suffering from endometriosis as well as influencing policy, as seen in the shared policy brief:

October 19, 2022

Other **Open Access**

First-person experiences of endometriosis in Catalonia: recommendations of women with endometriosis for improving health care services and public policies. TRANSFORM Policy Brief 2022

 Perucca Iannitelli, Carla

This Policy Brief is the result of a participatory research using citizen science methodologies where women have acted as co-researchers talking in first person about endometriosis in Catalonia. The research aims to explain and raise awareness about how endometriosis is experienced and how it affects people's overall health, as well as for the women themselves to generate first-person recommendations to improve diagnostic and care services. This Policy Brief is aimed at policy makers and health professionals.

This research has been made possible thanks to the active participation, motivation and enthusiasm of 20 women co-researchers who have been involved in the different phases of the scientific process. We are very grateful for their support, dedication and effort throughout the research, and we hope to achieve, as they wish, an impact on public health policies that will result in an improved approach to endometriosis at the health level that will improve the quality of life of present and future patients.

This citizen science pilot is part of the European TRANSFORM project (grant agreement N.872687). This document reflects the views only of the authors, and neither the European Commission nor the Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

<https://zenodo.org/record/7248108#.Y4SwRS0w1B1>

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

This white paper has focused on transparency, accessibility, and social responsibility in scientific research as well as highlighted the importance of *Open Science* and *Responsible Research and Innovation*. It has emphasised the need to make data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-useable, in accordance with the *FAIR data* principles. Building upon this and drawing from our experiences and subject-matter expertise, we provide the following recommendations for future stakeholder specific actions:

Individuals:

We recommend empowering, engaging, and educating individuals to ensure that all citizens have proper access to existing resources, fostering a more equal society. Stakeholder specific actions can be accommodated through:

- *Offering tools in multiple languages* to ensure better accessibility and reach.
- *Promote science education and engage the public* to foster a society that values and understands scientific advancements.

Practitioners:

From a practitioner's perspective, we recommend practitioners to *share knowledge, engage with online platforms* to share data and make greater use of *participatory methods toolkits*. To support these efforts, a dedicated RRI community has developed a comprehensive toolkit that serves as a practical resource for initiating and managing participatory projects. This toolkit offers guidelines on implementing participatory methods, along with a collection of 50 methods and techniques, including a comparative chart of 13 methods. You can access the toolkit through this link:

https://rri-tools.eu/-/participatory_methods_tools

Researchers:

From a researcher's perspective, we recommend that researchers reflect upon and carefully consider how they process, store, and collect their data. We have listed several considerations and actions which researchers could take to increase the accessibility of their data:

- Make greater use of *participatory research*, whenever relevant and possible:
 - Set up a participatory research agenda to identify stakeholders' unmet needs and help researchers include new perspectives in the research. *RRI tools* has listed a series of examples of methods for setting a participatory research agenda that can be used as inspiration: <https://rri-tools.eu/how-to-stk-pm-set-up-a-participatory-research-agenda>
 - Invite citizens into the research process, also younger researchers, to equip our future scientist and help children develop an interest in science.
 - Use the ECSA guidelines, <https://www.ecsa.ngo/documents/>.
 - Apply collaborative research.
- *Training in participatory action research* to raise awareness.
- *Sharing research findings through pre-prints*.
- Consider *FAIR data principles* and apply them to the extent possible:
 - Develop *Data management plans*.
 - Ensure accessibility of the research.
- Share code books and data from your research.
- Codes of research conduct.

Policy makers:

We recommend that policy-makers actively engage in discussions and take appropriate actions and measures that contribute to:

- *Promoting open access.*
- Increasing *citizen engagement.*
- Providing a framework for *science education.*
- Ensuring *cross-border sharing.*
- *Put citizens at the heart of decision-making:*
 - *RRI tools* have developed a guide that describes how public involvement can better address social issues, https://rri-tools.eu/-/people_participation_tools.
- Gender equality in decision-making bodies and labour conditions.
- Providing a *toolkit for open political decision-making:*
 - The government in the UK has already developed a toolkit for making policy for open, which others can be inspired by: <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/open-policy-making-toolkit>

Media:

We recommend the media to *share facts and numbers about gender imbalance* and also to *rewrite scientific articles into publications for citizens*, utilizing *infographics* for communication purposes to reach a much wider audience.

Further, *RRI tools* has developed a practical report discussing how to make the best use of expert advice in public dialogues and within the broader policy-making process, which we recommend the media to use, https://rri-tools.eu/-/use_experts_tools

NGO:

To promote citizen engagement and empower communities, we highly recommend NGOs to prioritize fostering *citizen engagement* through *science education* initiatives. Further, we encourage NGOs to actively *measure the impact of citizen science* initiatives and *evaluate the effectiveness of public engagement activities*.

This evaluation process allows NGOs to assess the outcomes and benefits of their initiatives, identify areas for improvement, and make data-informed decisions to enhance future programs.

Sponsors:

We recommend sponsors to embrace the role of *mission-driven innovation* by actively challenging existing norms and encouraging ground-breaking ideas. By fostering an environment that promotes creative thinking and risk-taking, sponsors can inspire researchers, entrepreneurs, and innovators to push boundaries and develop transformative solutions.

In addition, we encourage sponsors to *integrate RRI principles into funding* mechanisms and processes. This entails considering the societal impacts, ethical implications, and long-term sustainability of the projects they support.

RRI tools has provided a guide on how to incorporate the RRI principles in a funding call, <https://rri-tools.eu/how-to-stk-pm-incorporate-the-rri-principles-in-a-funding-call>.

Industry:

We highly recommend the industry to *prioritise gender equality* and actively work towards fostering a more inclusive and diverse environment. Specifically, we encourage the industry to *focus on developing innovative solutions* that address women's needs, especially by investing in and promoting *FemTech* solutions.

Furthermore, we recommend the industry to *contribute to open-source codes or software, invest in infrastructure and resources* and *establish partnerships and joint research projects*.

By implementing these recommendations, *industry* can drive positive change, promote innovation, and contribute to the overall development of society.

7. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the integration of *Open Science* and *Responsible Research and Innovation* is essential to address societal challenges and promote scientific progress and innovation.

The challenges identified in this white paper include lack of data sharing, insufficient funding, limited citizen engagement in the research process and the absence of dedicated attention to women's health. Here, *FemTech* can foster innovation, entrepreneurship, and economic growth in the sector of women's health.

Overcoming these challenges requires strategies to promote data transparency, ensure adequate funding, involve diverse stakeholders, and prioritise women's health research.

The presented five cases from the FEMaLe project and beyond show practical examples of how *Open Science* and *RRI* can be implemented.

Furthermore, the stakeholder specific actions contribute with concrete actions that can be implemented in society. We hope that this report can help raise awareness and inspire action towards positive change in data management.

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